

Optimal Management of a Hydro – Wind Energy System with Hydrogen Storage

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Abstract— The exploitation of renewable energy sources is nowadays a fundamental factor for the sustainable development and the transition to low a carbon energy production system. However, the fluctuating and unpredictable behavior of energy sources like wind complicates their integration into energy systems and they need to be coupled with storage systems to fully exploit their potential. The main objective of this paper is thus to develop a novel Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) algorithm capable of providing the optimal sizing and management of a hydrogen storage unit within a Hybrid Renewable Energy System (HRES) in which the produced energy is sold to the power grid. The algorithm has been validated with data from a case study located in Italy. The Hybrid Renewable Energy System under investigation is constituted by a hydropower plant, a wind turbine and a hydrogen storage system. The latter is composed of a Polymer Electrolyte Membrane (PEM) electrolyzer, four pressurized hydrogen tanks, and a PEM fuel cell. The optimal management has been obtained by responding to a unit commitment analysis.

Renewable Energies, Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems, Hydrogen Storage, Optimization Algorithm

I. INTRODUCTION

The energy generation sector is currently undergoing significant transformations worldwide in response to the need for a decarbonized energy system. This transition is primarily driven by the consequences of climate change and global warming resulting from human activities. In this evolving landscape, the crucial role of renewable energies becomes evident as they are instrumental in accelerating the transition. To facilitate this shift towards a sustainable energy future and reduce reliance on fossil fuels, the integration of renewable energy technologies is essential. Traditionally, the power generation system consisted of large-scale power plants. However, it is now transitioning towards decentralized energy systems based on distributed generation. These systems generate energy locally, even if they are connected to the main power network [1]. Despite the potential of renewable energy-based microgrids, their full deployment is hindered by certain limitations. These include the fluctuating and unpredictable nature of renewable energy sources and the complex design of Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems (HRES) [2]. To address these

challenges, the introduction of Energy Storage Systems (ESS) and the utilization of optimization techniques are critical components that can enhance the potential of distributed generation. ESSs play a vital role in the effective utilization of renewable energy systems and can be classified based on their technical characteristics. Each type of ESS is suited for specific applications [3]. Among the various ESSs, hydrogen storage systems are gaining prominence as effective alternatives in certain applications. These systems possess key characteristics that make them suitable for integration with HRESs. For instance, hydrogen storage systems exhibit high energy density, scalability, and conversion efficiency. They also offer rapid response times, enabling quick activation and release of stored energy when needed [4]. The use of hydrogen storage and optimization methods applied to HRESs has already been investigated demonstrating its effectiveness. For example, the authors of [5] proposed a novel approach based on an AI algorithm to increase the grid stability and lower the peak load of a wind - PV- hydrogen storage system. In [6], A two-layer collaborative optimization model of system design and operation has been applied to a renewable energy system that combines electricity storage, hydrogen storage, and heat storage demonstrating a significant reduction of CO₂ emissions. The authors of [7] applied a neural network–genetic algorithm optimization method to a PV – wind energy system with hydrogen storage demonstrating that adding the hydrogen storage system to the main system increases the reliability of the HRES and reduces dependency on grid electricity. In this paper, a MILP optimization algorithm has been applied to manage a grid connected HRES constituted by a hydropower plant, a wind turbine an electrolyser and a fuel cell using hydrogen as energy storage. The algorithm optimizes the operation of the electrolyzer and the charging – discharging phase of the hydrogen storage considering the hourly electrical energy cost to achieve the maximum profit.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Problem Definition and Case Study Description

A MILP algorithm as been applied to optimally manage the operations of a grid connected HRES constituted by a wind generator and a hydropower plant coupled with a

hydrogen storage system to achieve the maximum profit. The case study is based on the Sentino hydropower plant located in the city of Sassoferrato in the Marche Italian region. The data are referred to the power production of 2019. Since MILP algorithms compute the solution for a discretized time interval, simulations have been initially run considering a 24-hours span of time discretized every hour for a total of 24-time discretization steps to test the algorithm, than the simulation has been performed over a one month time span corresponding to January 2019. The computed data have been referred to characteristic days of operations to limit the computational resources required and the simulation time. This choice has been indicated also in other research papers as a good trade-off between results accuracy and computational resources [8]. The electricity price that has been considered in the simulation is the so-called PUN (unique national price), it refers to the wholesale reference price of electricity purchased on the IPEX – Market (Italian Power Exchange Market). The PUN represents the national weighted average of the zonal sales prices of electricity for each hour and for each day. The considered data, Fig. 1, are referred to January 2019 and have been provided by the Energy Market Manager (GME) website [9]. The scheme of the HRES is shown in Fig. 2. The models of the hydropower, wind and storage systems are described in the next sections.

Figure 1. PUN trend for January 28th of 2019

Figure 2. HRES scheme

B. Hydropower System Model

The reference plant is a run of a river HPP, therefore an upper reservoir is not present and the turbined water flow is strongly ruled by the water level of the river reach upstream the withdrawal. In hydropower plants, the produced power depends on different factors like discharge and hydraulic head as the main ones. Eq. (1) reports the formula used to compute the power output from a hydro turbine plant.

$$P_{\text{hydro}} = \rho \cdot g \cdot H \cdot Q \cdot \eta \quad (1)$$

Where P_{hydro} is the output power (kW), ρ is the water density (1000 kg/m^3), g is the gravity acceleration (9.81 m/s^2), Q is the water flow rate or water discharge (m^3/s), H is the hydraulic head (m) and η is the overall plant efficiency. The power produced by the hydropower plant has been directly obtained by an experimental measurement of the water discharges. Sentino hydropower plant is made of 2 Kaplan hydro-turbines with a rated power of 220 kW, a discharge water flowrate of $4.6 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and a hydraulic head H of 6.5 m. By applying Eq. (1) starting from the technical data of the hydropower plant and the measured waterflow data, the hourly power production by hydropower plant can be computed. The hydropower production is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Hourly hydropower production data for 28th of January 2019

C. Wind Turbine Model

The amount of electricity generated by a wind turbine relies on the wind speed at the central hub. By utilizing the power curve provided by the manufacturer, the generated power can be determined based on the known wind speeds. Typically, anemometers are positioned at a lower height compared to the hub. Hence, Eq. (2) calculates the effective wind speed using a commonly employed formula for heights below 150m. This equation accounts for various heights and incorporates the surface roughness of the specific installation site, with typical values mentioned in [10].

$$w_{\text{hub}} = w_h \cdot \ln(z_{\text{hub}}/z_0)/\ln(z_{\text{anem}}/z_0) \quad (2)$$

The power output of a wind turbine is determined by the wind speeds at the hub height, and this is calculated using the power curve. The power generation begins when the wind speed reaches a specific value called the cut-in speed, denoted as $w_{\text{cut-in}}$, as explained in Eq. (3). As the wind speed increases, the power output also increases until it reaches the rated value P_R , which corresponds to a wind speed of w_R . From w_R to the cut-out speed $w_{\text{cut-out}}$, the power output remains constant at P_R ; it no longer increases beyond this point. To prevent failures, the turbine ceases power generation beyond the cut-out speed. Fig. 4 illustrates the power curve of a 250 kW wind turbine that could be potentially installed at the analyzed site, while Fig. 5 the hourly wind speed data.

$$\begin{aligned}
P_{WT} &= 0, \text{ if } w_t < w_{\text{cut-in}} \text{ or } w_t > w_{\text{cut-out}} \\
P_{WT} &= P_i, \text{ if } w_{\text{cut-in}} \leq w_t < w_R \\
P_{WT} &= P_R, \text{ if } w_R \leq w_t \leq w_{\text{cut-out}}
\end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Figure 4. Possible power curve of a wind turbine eligible for the site of interest

Figure 5. Hourly wind speed data

D. Hydrogen Storage System Model

The hydrogen storage system comprises three key components: a 150 kW electrolyzer, four 850-liter H_2 storage tanks, and a 250 kW H_2 fuel cell. It operates by converting wind and hydro turbine-generated energy into hydrogen via the electrolyzer, storing it in tanks, and converting it back to electricity with the fuel cell. The energy capacity of each component and the existing energy in the system, along with generator behavior and energy prices, influence energy delivery and storage for each interval, described by Eq. (4).

$$E_{st}(t) = E_{\text{stored}}(t-1) + [E_{\text{wt-strg}}(t) + E_{\text{hydro-strg}}(t) - E_{\text{strg-grid}}(t)] \quad (4)$$

E. MILP Optimization Model

The MILP (Mixed Integer Linear Programming) optimization algorithm is a robust method for solving linear optimization problems. It involves defining an objective function, constraints expressed as linear equations or inequalities, and decision variables [11]. The aim is to maximize the objective function while adhering to the constraints. In this study, the focus is on finding the optimal

management strategy for a 24-hour storage unit with discrete time intervals. The MILP algorithm, implemented using the MATLAB Optimization Toolbox [12], assigns values to variables and constraints to yield the optimal solution. This choice of MILP is due to its compatibility with the problem's linearity, although it requires more computational resources compared to heuristics, it guarantees an optimal solution. Fig. 6 reports the MILP optimization algorithm flow chart.

Figure 6. MILP optimization algorithm flow chart

The algorithm aims to maximize the system's profit, which is determined by the power plant's gross income minus its costs. These characteristics are closely tied to the components of the power plant. Each element of the H_2 storage system has a cost, denoted as C_i , which includes both the investment cost ($C_{\text{inv-EC}}$ for the electrolyzer, $C_{\text{h2-tank}}$ for the hydrogen tank and $C_{\text{inv-FC}}$ for the fuel cell) and the operation and maintenance cost ($C_{\text{O\&M}}$). The objective function incorporates the total cost, as expressed in Eq. (5).

$$C_{\text{tot}} = (C_{\text{inv-EC}} + C_{\text{O\&M-EC}}) + C_{\text{h2-tank}} + (C_{\text{inv-FC}} + C_{\text{O\&M-FC}}) \quad (5)$$

The gross income is given by the sale of the produced energy at the corresponding PUN price PUN. The actual objective function is reported in Eq. (6).

$$\text{Max } [(E_{\text{WT-grid}} + E_{\text{hyd-grid}} + E_{\text{FC-grid}} \cdot \eta_{\text{FC}}) \cdot \text{PUN} - C_{\text{tot}}] \quad (6)$$

Where $E_{\text{WT-grid}}$ and $E_{\text{hyd-grid}}$ are the amount of energy produced by the wind turbine and the hydro turbine directly sold to the grid, $E_{\text{FC-grid}}$ is the energy released by the fuel cell unit and therefore sold to the grid. The goal of the MILP algorithm is the maximization of the objective function by assigning a value to the decision variables. Therefore, the optimization variables are strongly related to the objective

function output. In the case study, the involved variables are the energy produced by the hydropower plant to be injected to the grid; the energy produced by the hydropower plant to be injected to the storage system, the energy produced by the wind turbine to be injected to the grid and the energy produced by the wind turbine to be injected to the storage system. Each variable is constituted by a number of values equal to the number of hours of the considered period. The decision variables are also subjected to technical constraints that simulate the limitations that have to be considered when designing real HRES. The constraints are equalities and inequalities set to limit the values that the algorithm can assign to the optimization variables in his task of finding the optimal solution. Such constraints can be related to technological, economic or geometrical limitations and are set *a priori*. The defined constraints for the optimization problem under investigation are expressed by the following equations.

$$E_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) + E_{\text{hyd-grid}}(i) \leq E_{\text{p-hyd}}(i) \quad (7)$$

$$E_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) + E_{\text{WT-grid}}(i) \leq E_{\text{p-WT}}(i) \quad (8)$$

$$E_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) + E_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) \leq C_{\text{in-max-ec}} \quad (9)$$

$$\sum E_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) + \sum E_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) - \sum E_{\text{FC-grid}}(i) \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\sum E_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) + \sum E_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) - \sum E_{\text{FC-grid}}(i) \leq C_{\text{strg}} \quad (11)$$

$$E_{\text{FC-grid}}(i) \geq E_{\text{minout-FC}} \cdot \text{isOn}_{\text{FC-grid}}(i) \quad (12)$$

$$E_{\text{FC-grid}}(i) \leq E_{\text{maxout-FC}} \cdot \text{isOn}_{\text{FC-grid}}(i) \quad (13)$$

$$E_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) \geq E_{\text{minin-EC}} \cdot \text{isOn}_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) \quad (14)$$

$$E_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) \leq C_{\text{maxin-EC}} \cdot \text{isOn}_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) \quad (15)$$

$$E_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) \geq E_{\text{minin-EC}} \cdot \text{isOn}_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) \quad (16)$$

$$E_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) \leq C_{\text{maxin-EC}} \cdot \text{isOn}_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) \quad (17)$$

$$\text{isOn}_{\text{FC-grid}}(i) + \text{isOn}_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) \leq 1 \quad (18)$$

$$\text{isOn}_{\text{FC-grid}}(i) + \text{isOn}_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) \leq 1 \quad (19)$$

$$\text{isOn}_{\text{FC-grid}}(i) + \text{isOn}_{\text{hyd-EC}}(i) + \text{isOn}_{\text{WT-EC}}(i) \leq 2 \quad (20)$$

Eq. (7) ensures that the total energy used or sold cannot exceed the energy produced by the hydro turbine for a given hour. Similarly, Eq. (8) imposes the same restriction for the energy generated by the wind turbine. Eq. (9) sets a limit on the combined energy sent from both turbines to the electrolyzer, ensuring it does not exceed the electrolyzer's input capacity. Eq. (10) and Eq. (11) control the state of charge of the storage system, keeping it above zero and within the maximum energy storage capacity. Eq. (12) and

Eq. (13) govern the energy output of the fuel cell, guaranteeing it meets the minimum and maximum energy output requirements. Eq. (14) and Eq. (15) define the acceptable range for energy sent from the hydropower plant to the electrolyzer, while Eq. (16) and Eq. (17) do the same for the energy sent from the wind turbine. Finally, Eq. (18), Eq. (19), and Eq. (20) prevent simultaneous charging and discharging of the storage system, ensuring the electrolyzer and fuel cell operate independently.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To validate the functionality of the algorithm, a simulation was conducted using 24 hours of data. Fig. 7 illustrates the power generated by renewable sources on the 28th of January, along with the corresponding trend of the Electricity National Price (PUN). The PUN is characterized by a fluctuating trend that does not necessarily matches with the renewable production. This specific date was chosen as a representative day for the entire month. Fig. 8 shows how the assets of the energy system operate storing or injecting to the grid the electrical energy production. It can be concluded that the optimization algorithm performed effectively. The behavior of the storage system aligns with the expected pattern: charging occurs when the energy price falls below a threshold of 0.041 €/kWh, while discharging takes place when the energy price exceeds an upper threshold of 0.075 €/kWh. During hours when the PUN falls between these thresholds, the power generated by wind and hydro sources is directly sold to the grid at the corresponding PUN price. Furthermore, the simulation was extended to cover the duration of one month, specifically January 2019. The optimization algorithm determines the optimal hours for selling energy, storing energy as hydrogen, and converting stored hydrogen back into energy for selling to the grid. The results are presented in Fig. 9. The simulation demonstrates that the system efficiently stores energy during periods of low PUN trends and discharges from the storage tank during high PUN trends. Consequently, the novel algorithm effectively selects whether it is advantageous to sell or store the energy production based on fluctuations in energy prices.

Figure 7. Hydropower production, wind power production and PUN trend for 28th of January

Figure 8. Optimization algorithm results for 24h test

Figure 9. Optimization algorithm results for January 2019

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study focused on investigating a HRES at the Sentino hydropower plant in Italy, with a specific emphasis on hydrogen production and storage. The main objective was to develop an innovative optimization algorithm to effectively manage the hydrogen storage unit within the hybrid energy system. The aim of this optimization was to maximize profit, which was determined by selling the stored energy at the prevailing energy market price, represented by the PUN (Electricity National Price). The simulations conducted in this study revealed that the optimal schedule for the storage system involved charging it by diverting the generated energy to the electrolyzer when the energy price fell below a certain low-threshold. This process allowed to produce green hydrogen, which was then stored in dedicated tanks. Conversely, the storage system was discharged by supplying the hydrogen to the fuel cell unit when the energy price exceeded a certain high threshold. This enabled the sale of the energy generated through this conversion process at the highest possible price. To validate the functionality of the algorithm, it was tested on a 24-hour scenario and subsequently extended to cover an entire month. The results confirmed that the algorithm successfully optimized the management of the storage system, demonstrating its effectiveness in maximizing profit within the hybrid energy system. Although the utilization of the HRES with Fuel Cells could be technically convenient, it is still a very expensive method as the investment cost are higher and the efficiency is lower compared to already existing competitor systems.

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